

STUDY OF THE PROSPECTS FOR HEALTH CARE OF CHILDREN WITH HEART DEFECTS

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ABSTRACT

This review article is devoted to the current problem of pediatric and adolescent cardiology - congenital heart defects in children. Based on extensive modern domestic and foreign literature, issues of epidemiology, developmental risk factors, problems of somatic health, cognitive development and psycho-social status of children with congenital heart disease, methods of early diagnosis, principles of prevention and rehabilitation are analyzed. Modern molecular genetic aspects of the pathogenesis of congenital heart disease are covered. The importance of socio-biological, socio-economic and environmental factors in the development and prognosis of congenital heart disease is presented. The summary points to the value of screening women of childbearing age, fetus and newborn (ultrasound, biochemical) for the presence of placental markers that help predict the risk of developing chromosomal abnormalities, etc. The importance and need for neonatal screening for critical congenital heart defects, as well as a team approach, is noted with the participation of all specialists in the development of personalized methods of treatment and rehabilitation of children with congenital heart disease, which will allow the correct organization of appropriate assistance to children of this contingent in the early stages and after surgical treatment and will lead to a reduction in child mortality and morbidity.

Relevance. Congenital diseases, which cause a significant number of embryonic and fetal deaths, occupy a leading position in the structure of childhood morbidity, disability, and mortality and represent a major health and social problem worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), "...240,000 newborn babies and 170,000 children aged one month to five years die each year from congenital diseases within the first 28 days of life. These diseases can lead to long-term disability, which has a significant impact on individuals, their families, health systems, and society. As the mortality rate of newborns and children under five years of age decreases, the share of congenital diseases among the causes of death

in newborns and children under five years of age increases. The most severe congenital diseases include heart defects, neural tube defects, and Down syndrome.” Congenital heart defects (CHDs) are a large, nosologically diverse group of congenital anomalies whose development is determined by the complex interaction of environmental and genetic factors. CHDs are an important medical and social problem in pediatric and adolescent cardiology. In terms of incidence, they rank third after congenital defects of the musculoskeletal system and central nervous system. Among all malformations, congenital heart defects (including cases of intrauterine fetal death and early miscarriages) account for 40%. Therefore, monitoring the dynamics of these indicators, as well as analyzing trends in the prevalence and incidence of congenital heart defects in children at the regional level, are of great importance for the timely planning of surgical correction and treatment and preventive measures. According to various sources, the prevalence of congenital heart defects in children in the early 2000s varied significantly and ranged from 4 to 50 cases per 1,000 live births, which is explained by different assessment criteria. The incidence of moderate and severe congenital heart defects among US children was approximately 6 cases per 1,000 live births, increasing to 19/1,000 when including children with bicuspid aortic valves and to 75/1,000 when including punctate muscular ventricular septal defects. In recent years, some stabilization has been observed in this indicator, with approximately 1.5 million children born with congenital heart defects worldwide annually. The prevalence of severe congenital heart defects has also increased over time, likely due to improved diagnostic methods for congenital heart defects and the prevention of antenatal and infant mortality. Thus, the results of the study, covering the period 1985-2000, showed an increase in the proportion of severe congenital heart defects in the pediatric population by 22%. The development and prognosis of CHD are influenced by many factors, including the presence of extracardiac diseases in children with congenital heart defects, nutrition and feeding of children; genetic factors, socio-economic and socio-biological factors, and environmental factors. CHD can be isolated or part of a complex of multiple congenital malformations. The leading extracardiac disorders in multiple congenital malformations were anomalies of the musculoskeletal system (up to 35%), gastrointestinal tract (25%), and genitourinary system (23%). According to research in 2013, almost 40% of children had combined congenital heart defects (a combination of 2 or more congenital heart defects in one child). Thirty percent of children with congenital heart defects had multiple congenital malformations: 8% had musculoskeletal anomalies, 8% had craniofacial dimorphism, 5% had gastrointestinal anomalies, 4% had urinary system anomalies, 3% had hemangiomas and eye pathology, and 2% had pulmonary defects [51]. The most frequent association with defects of other organs and systems was observed in cases of atrioventricular canal, coarctation of the aorta, functionally single ventricle, pulmonary artery stenosis, as well as hypoplastic right heart syndrome, double outlet right ventricle, and transposition of the great vessels. In newborns with congenital heart defects, there is an increased risk of feeding difficulties before and after surgery; the incidence of dysphagia in children in this group ranges from 14% to 51%. Children with congenital heart defects of various age groups experience more difficulties associated with enteral feeding than their healthy peers. Feeding problems lead to significant disruptions in the quality of life of children with congenital heart defects and their families, as they impact short- and long-term neurodevelopment related to

growth and nutrition, sensory regulation, and social-emotional connections with parents and other caregivers. Newborns with congenital heart defects require a personalized approach to enteral feeding, depending on the types of cardiac surgery they have undergone. Children with congenital heart defects have been shown to have behavioral problems. Children born with genetic syndromes have a significantly higher risk of cognitive impairment. Interactions between pathogens and brain cells are also important for brain development. The brains of full-term infants with congenital heart defects (CHD) were smaller than those of infants without CHD born prematurely at 35 weeks. This is two-thirds the size a fetus should have at 40 weeks. This means that children born with CHD are delayed in brain development by approximately a month and thus are born late [3]. Children with more severe CHD have more severe cognitive impairment [31]. It has been found that children with congenital heart defects (CHD) can experience delays across the entire spectrum of neurodevelopmental development, including motor, cognitive, language, and behavioral development. The American Heart Association and the American Academy of Pediatrics recommend routine surveillance, screening, and evaluation of this high-risk population of children for early detection and intervention to prevent neurodevelopmental delays. A number of studies have been conducted to investigate genomic imbalances using DNA microarrays and small noncoding RNAs in the pathogenesis of CHD. MicroRNAs have been found to coordinate cardiac development and stimulate pathological processes within it, and also serve as biomarkers for postoperative complications following surgical correction of CHD. According to Russian scientists, the determination of CHD is associated with immune regulation genes. According to the WHO, socioeconomic factors, including low income, may be an indirect factor in the development of congenital diseases, which are more common in low-income families and resource-poor countries. It is estimated that approximately 94% of major congenital disorders occur in low- and middle-income countries. As an indirect determinant, this higher risk is associated with possible lack of access by pregnant women to nutritious foods, increased exposure to factors such as infection and alcohol, or lesser access to health care and screening. Numerous studies have demonstrated the importance of sociobiological factors in the development and prognosis of CHD. Preconception and periconceptional health care (preconception and periconceptional screening) includes basic reproductive health measures, as well as medical genetic screening and parental counseling. Preconceptional screening is particularly important in countries where consanguineous marriages are common. Periconceptional screening includes screening of mothers of reproductive age, screening for alcohol use, tobacco use, and other risks. Screening (ultrasound and biochemical imaging) for placental markers is crucial, as it helps predict the risk of chromosomal abnormalities, neural tube defects, and other conditions. Newborn screening helps identify the risk of developing congenital malformations and organize appropriate care for children, thereby reducing infant mortality and morbidity associated with congenital malformations. Given the high mortality rate associated with late diagnosis of critical forms of congenital heart defects, increasing attention is currently being paid to the implementation of neonatal screening for these types of defects..

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